

Socio-economic and environmental consequences of the Caspian Sea level decline for coastal communities in Azerbaijan

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Abstract: The Caspian Sea level reached a historic minimum of -29.45 m (Baltic system) in 2025, exposing approximately 38,000 hectares along Azerbaijan's coast. It was found that this decline has triggered soil salinization and water scarcity, adversely affecting critical economic sectors: oil and gas (30.6–35.3% of GDP), fisheries (20-30% catch reduction), transport (dredging costs up to US\$200 million), and agriculture (15-25% yield decline). It was emphasized that socio-economic impacts include potential loss of 20,000-50,000 jobs, increased unemployment (10-15%), and displacement risks for 50,000 -100,000 people. Furthermore, changes in Caspian Sea water levels can cause environmental harm and socio-economic impacts such as business damage, livelihood loss, forced migration, and infrastructure degradation in coastal areas. Projected further declines by 2100 necessitate urgent adaptation through infrastructure modernization, bioremediation, and strengthened regional cooperation. It was noted that the Caspian States are developing an Action Plan for the period 2025-2035, in close cooperation with UNEP, which aims to promote sustainable resource management and mitigate environmental and socio-economic risks.

Keywords: *sustainable development, socio-economic and environmental indicators, Caspian Sea level decline, climate change impacts, coastal community vulnerability*

Introduction

Over the past few decades, the level of the Caspian Sea has shown a steady downward trend, which has become particularly pronounced since 2005. The average annual decline is 10-15 cm, though some estimates put it at 20–30 cm. Between 1995 and 2025, the sea level dropped by 190 cm, reaching a historic low of -29.45 m (according to the Baltic reference system) in 2025, the lowest level in the last 400 years. (CASPCOM, 2025) According to data from the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources, the level has dropped by 0.93 metres over the past five years, by 1.5 metres over ten years, and by 2.5 metres over 30 years.

The overall deterioration of the Caspian Sea environment is due to a combination of factors, including global warming, human activity and inefficient management of water resources. These factors are interrelated and contribute to a decline in sea levels, which has serious consequences for biodiversity and the socio-economic situation of coastal states. The main reasons for this decline are increased evaporation due to rising temperatures and altered wind patterns, reduced river inflows (especially from the Volga), and hydrological changes caused by human activities, such as river regulation and agricultural irrigation. The construction of dams on the Volga since the Soviet era has significantly reduced river inflows, with a critical impact on maintaining the level of the Caspian Sea. The Volga River basin covers an extensive area of around 1.38 million km² and contains nine dams within the Caspian Sea basin. These structures account for over 75% of the total water flowing into the sea, with a combined capacity of 223 km³. Since the 1980s, fluctuations in the Volga's flow have been caused by reduced precipitation in the upper reaches of the river, as well as the impact of dam construction in its catchment area (EIAS, 2024).

The combined impact of these processes is leading to a critical decline in the volume of water in the Caspian Sea, threatening the ecosystems and economic stability of the region. It was estimated that temperatures in Azerbaijan are projected to rise at a faster rate than the global average, with potential warming of 4.7°C by the 2090s over the 1986–2005 baseline, under the highest emissions pathway (RCP8.5) (World Bank, 2021). Forecasts based on CMIP6

models suggest that the level of the Caspian Sea will decline by a further 8-14 metres by 2100. This will reduce the area of the water body by around 25% and expose up to 93,000 km² of new land. According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2024), the water level in the Caspian Sea could drop by 18 metres by the end of the 21st century, resulting in far-reaching environmental, humanitarian and economic consequences.

Azerbaijan's coastal areas, which stretch 825 km along the Absheron Peninsula, Baku and the southern regions from the Kura Delta to Lenkoran and Astara, are the most vulnerable due to the shallow waters in the north and southeast. This leads to land exposure (approximately 38,000 hectares), desertification, soil salinization and a shortage of freshwater. These socio-economic consequences affect 12 administrative districts, which are home to over 4 million people (including those in Baku), accounting for up to 40% of the country's population (Aliyev et al., 2021; Imrani, 2021, WB and ADB, 2021, World Bank, 2025).

Changes in the water level of the Caspian Sea can have significant environmental and socio-economic consequences, including damage to businesses in coastal areas, loss of livelihoods, forced migration and degradation of infrastructure. These negative effects could outweigh any potential trade benefits brought about by the development of the Middle Corridor.

Key economic sectors, such as oil and gas, fisheries, transport, tourism and agriculture, are already experiencing direct losses. This exacerbates the risk of increased poverty, particularly among women, young people and socially vulnerable groups. The livelihoods of millions of people, as well as food security, depend directly on the ecosystem services provided by the Caspian Sea. The loss of these services will have serious and long-term socio-economic consequences.

This article aims to analyze and evaluate the socio-economic impact of the declining water level of the Caspian Sea on coastal communities in Azerbaijan. The purpose is to identify key challenges and develop recommendations to mitigate the negative effects and support the region's sustainable development.

Research methodology

This study employs a comprehensive interdisciplinary approach based on the analysis of literature reviews and empirical data. A systematic review of scientific publications and reports on Caspian Sea level dynamics and its socio-economic consequences for coastal communities in Azerbaijan was conducted. The data obtained from the literature was supplemented by an analysis of hydrological observations and statistics from official sources.

This combined approach allows for the integration of theoretical knowledge and practical information to gain a deep understanding of the socio-economic and environmental consequences of sea level decline, identify key challenges, and develop recommendations for the sustainable development of coastal regions.

Analysis and discussion

1. Demographic and territorial indicators

The coasts of Azerbaijan, Iran, and the Russian Federation are the most densely populated areas of the Caspian Sea. In these Caspian countries, the consequences of climate threats for urban and rural populations will be most significant in absolute terms. According to UNEP's Caspian Sea Fluctuations and Climate Change assessment (2024), between 80 and 100 million people living in the Caspian region may be exposed to climate change risks.

More than 4.3 million people live in Azerbaijan's coastal areas and its largest cities. Baku which sits on the Caspian Coast, accounted for approximately \$39 billion (71%) of the country's GDP. These areas contain 75% of the country's industrial resources and will be directly or indirectly affected by sea-level fluctuations, increased flooding, severe droughts and desertification (World Bank and ADB, 2021). The total area of the coastal regions is 14,780 km². The average population density is 291.1 people per km², and there are 754 settlements (Table 1). In this regard, sea level rise will affect the livelihoods of coastal communities, which are already experiencing a sharp decline in economic activities such as fishing and agriculture.

Table 1. The population of the coastal areas of Azerbaijan

Rayon/Region	Area, thousand, km²	Population, thousands of people	Population density, km²	Populated areas
1. Khachmaz	1,06	175,4	166	151
2. Shabran	1,09	58,8	54	69
3. Siyazan	0,7	42	60	34
4. Khyzy	1,67	16,8	10	29
5. Sumgayit	0,12	427,6	3563	3
6. Absheron	2,11	434	206	17
7. Baku	2,1	2351,3	1120	60
8. Salyan	1,6	140,3	88	51
9. Neftchala	1,45	87,6	60	52
10. Lankaran	1,54	228,1	148	93
11. Masally	0,72	227,7	316	103
12. Astara	0,62	112,8	182	92
Total	14,78	4302,4	291,1	754

Source: State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan.

Over 2.3 million people, including residents of Baku and surrounding densely populated areas in the Absheron region, are at risk of migration due to loss of land and jobs. According to UNDP estimates (2022), poverty levels in vulnerable communities could increase by 10-20%. Azerbaijan's State Concept of Migration Management (2004) classifies persons displaced by changes in the Caspian Sea level as environmental migrants.

It should be noted that from 1995 to 2022, the area of land reclaimed from the sea in 11 districts at a level of -28.40 m BS was about 37,000 ha, indicating a significant change in the coastline and expansion of coastal areas (Aliyev et al., 2025). This change has led to land degradation processes, including desertification and a 20-30% reduction in soil fertility in southern areas, and has exacerbated salinization in certain coastal areas, such as Salyan and Neftchala. The greatest losses have been recorded in the Neftchala district and in the Gyzylagach State Reserve, where the coastline has receded between 1 and 5 kilometers from the shore (Table 2).

Table 2. Change in coastal area as a result of the decline of the Caspian Sea

Rayon	Coastline length (km)	Exposed area (ha)
1. Khachmaz	66	1573
2. Shabran	20,7	790
3. Siyazan	39,6	464
4. Khyzy	26,1	388
5. Baku	289,6	2029
6. Salyan	11,7	46
7. Neftchala	94,6	10 085
8. Gyzylagach State Reserve	102	18 164
9. Masally	31,5	2903
10. Lankaran	35,1	312
11. Astara	21,1	68
Total	738,1	36 822

The negative consequences of changes in the Caspian Sea level are particularly acute in the coastal zone of Azerbaijan, where the greatest impact is felt in the southern territories - from the Kura River delta to the coastal areas of Lankaran and Astara. The main factors that increase the vulnerability of these areas are the terrain and geomorphological features of the coast, which make the territory prone to flooding and erosion (Lebedev et al., 2005; Aliyev, 2021).

In 2020, the intrusion of seawater from the Caspian Sea into the Kura River delta in Azerbaijan, expanding up to 66 km towards the cities of Salyan and Neftchala was observed. This negatively affected the water quality and ecological balance of the delta. The main reasons for this were changes in the hydrological regime, fluctuations in the level of the Caspian Sea and anthropogenic factors, such as abstraction of water for agricultural use and land reclamation works in the upper reaches of the river. These factors caused an increase in salinity and allowed salty seawater to penetrate freshwater areas of the delta. This poses a threat to the delta's ecosystem, including fish spawning grounds and other aquatic life, and negatively impacts economic activities related to fishing and agriculture in the region (EUWI+, 2021; Akhundov, Mamedov et al., 2021).

In this context, communities and individuals living in low-lying areas and unplanned coastal and riverine settlements are particularly vulnerable. They are exposed to significant risks from both flooding and drought, the latter of which exacerbates the impact of climate change. Furthermore, as populations grow and material assets accumulate, the potential scale of losses in the event of an emergency increases. The most affected groups include the elderly, people with disabilities, women responsible for household management, children, and seasonal workers and migrants employed in affected sectors. A comprehensive approach to risk assessment and the development of adaptation measures aimed at reducing the vulnerability of the region's population and infrastructure is therefore required.

2. Economic indicators by sector

The share of the oil and gas industry in the country's GDP has declined from about 40% over the past six years to approximately 30.6% in 2024, indicating diversification of the economy and reduced dependence on the oil industry. In 2024, the non-oil sector's share of GDP was about 67.8%. Oil production in the country is declining, with production in 2024 forecast at about 29.2 million tons, below the peak levels of the past decade.

Declining production and the depletion of major fields threaten the country's critical infrastructure, including pipelines and production platforms in the Absheron region. Potential economic losses from production restrictions could reach 5-10% of annual production, based on an assessment of risks to the Volga-Caspian Canal (Ministry of Economy, 2025).

Fisheries and aquaculture. The Caspian Sea plays a key role in the economies of coastal regions, providing important natural resources and supporting the livelihoods of millions of people. It should be noted that the Caspian Sea is home to about 90% of the world's sturgeon population. At the same time, it is of great importance for the biodiversity of Central Asia and Europe, being home to over 300 endemic species of invertebrates and about 76 endemic species of fish, including the unique Caspian seal (*Pusa caspica*) (UNEP, 2024).

Over the past decade, commercial catches have declined by 20-30% due to the shallowing of the sea, deterioration of oxygen conditions, and increased water pollution, further highlighting the seriousness of environmental challenges and their economic consequences for the region. (Akhundov, Mamedov, 2021, Court et al., 2025).

In addition, the decline in the Caspian Sea level is changing the habitat and migration routes of sturgeon and other commercial species, exacerbating the problems of their reproduction and harvesting.

Catches of commercial fish species in Azerbaijan during the period 1990-2024 were characterized by significant fluctuations from 18,000 to 8,000 tons due to the depletion of fish stocks in the Caspian Sea, illegal fishing, and catch quota regulations. In 2015-2022, catches were low, amounting to 626-1,800 tons of the allocated quota due to the deterioration of resources. However, recent years have seen a significant increase in commercial fish catches,

mainly kilka, with annual catches of around 8,000 tons. These factors have a negative impact on ecosystems and cause a decline in biological resources, leading to significant income losses for 10,000-15,000 fishermen in coastal areas.

The main commercial species include kilka (up to 80% of the total catch), mullet, herring, bream, roach, carp, pike perch, and kutum. At the same time, aquaculture is developing, aimed at reducing the pressure on wild populations and increasing commercial fish production in ponds and artificial reservoirs. In recent years, Azerbaijan has been actively breeding young fish of valuable species - sturgeon, salmon, and carp - releasing tens of millions of individuals into natural water bodies to restore fish stocks.

According to satellite observations for the period 1992-2022, the coastal zone of the Caspian Sea in the Gyzyllagach Bay has shifted approximately 5-6 km into the sea (Bakhishov, 2023). According to the results obtained, 30% of water bodies and 52% of wetlands have been lost within the protected area. The dynamics of the changes indicate that they are caused by a reduction in the flow of fresh water entering the reserve, as well as a drop in the water level in the Caspian Sea by more than 1 m over the past 15 years. In the southern regions, declining fish stocks are forcing fishermen to go further out to sea, increasing fuel costs.

Thus, significant environmental impacts on the economy include increased soil salinisation, wetland degradation and the deterioration of other wetland ecosystems, a reduction in biodiversity and in the catch of commercial fish species, a decline in the quality of surface and groundwater resources, and a fall in the services provided by ecosystems. These changes lead to a decline in agricultural productivity and the deterioration of habitats for fish and other aquatic organisms. They also lead to the depletion of natural resources and increased costs for restoration and protection. Taken together, these factors negatively impact the sustainable development of regions and require a comprehensive approach to natural resource management and environmental protection.

Transportation. The Baku International Sea Trade Port, including the new Alat economic zone, is a key transport hub of the “Middle Corridor” (Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, TITR) with a cargo turnover of approximately 10-15 million tons per year. In recent years, the decline in the level of the Caspian Sea has led to significant silting of the water area and a reduction in the draught of ships by 7-10 cm per year, which creates additional difficulties for navigation. To maintain regulatory depths, large-scale dredging is required annually, with a total cost in the Caspian estimated at US\$100–200 million (EIAS, 2024).

If the sea level drops to -30 meters, the area of Baku Bay could shrink from 50 km² to 10-15 km², and the volume of water could decrease from 0.7 km³ to 0.1 km³ (i.e., by 90%). This will lead to a reduction in the permissible draught of ships - for dry cargo ships, the reduction will be 300-400 tonnes, and tankers will only be loaded to 80% of their full capacity. As a result, the cost of dredging will increase. In this regard, Azerbaijan is building new dredgers to maintain the port's navigability and safety.

This will negatively affect navigability, cause congestion, and increase cargo traffic jams in the port by 20–30%, which will affect the throughput and transit potential of the entire transport system in the region. Despite these challenges, the Port of Baku has demonstrated steady growth in container throughput, which increased by 48-54% in 2025, demonstrating the importance and strategic significance of this transport hub for Azerbaijan and the whole of Eurasia (Port of Baku). A further decline in the level of the Caspian Sea will significantly limit the size of vessels capable of safely navigating its waters, which could lead to significant congestion in Caspian ports and reduce the economic efficiency of trans-Caspian cargo transportation. Restrictions on ship draft and reduced depth of passage require increased expenditure on dredging, which is costly and ongoing.

Tourism. Tourism contributes approximately 6.2% to the GDP of Azerbaijan's coastal areas (including Baku and Lankaran) and employs over 423,000 people. The state is actively investing in the development of tourism infrastructure, especially in the regions. New hotels are being built, roads are being reconstructed, cultural centers and eco-routes are being opened,

which contributes to the growth of tourist activity and the economic development of the regions. These goals and indicators are enshrined in the official tourism development strategy aimed at diversifying the economy and strengthening regional tourism in Azerbaijan by 2030.

According to the Tourism Agency, by 2030 the tourism sector's contribution to Azerbaijan's GDP could reach 11.5 billion manats, and tourism's share in the non-oil and gas sector of the economy could reach 8.2%. Tourism revenues are expected to grow to 7.4 billion manats. At the same time, regional centers, including coastal ones, play an important role, providing about 46% of overnight stays for foreign tourists and creating about 5.8% of jobs in the tourism sector throughout the country.

Desertification and degradation of beaches in coastal areas lead to significant economic losses. The loss of beach quality and area contributes to a decrease in income from health resort vacations by approximately 10-20%. This is equivalent to threats to about 50,000 jobs in the tourism sector in coastal areas. The decline in the water level in the Caspian Sea further exacerbates the environmental and economic situation, directly affecting the attractiveness of coastal tourism and the overall socio-economic development of the region.

Agriculture. In the southern regions of Azerbaijan, salinization and declining groundwater levels affect approximately 20-30 thousand hectares of irrigated land, leading to a 15-25% decrease in crop yields.

According to the MENR (2025), the intensity of extreme weather events has increased sharply in Azerbaijan in recent years. The number of floods has increased 80-fold, the duration of droughts by 80%, and the number of days with temperatures above 30 degrees by 6 times. The number of forest fires has increased fivefold, cases of strong winds 12-fold, and the frequency of precipitation has increased sixfold. As a result of these climate changes, the volume of water resources entering the country has decreased by 30%. Due to the water shortage, about 100,000 farmers whose farms depend on irrigation systems are experiencing difficulties. As of 2025, about 17% of irrigated land in the country is characterized by low salinity, 8.4% by moderate salinity, and 3.3% by high salinity, which has a significant negative impact on the agricultural sector.

According to data from the Ministry of Agriculture of Azerbaijan (2025), only 11-12% of irrigated land (out of 1.485 million hectares) uses modern irrigation systems, which exacerbates water shortages and salinization. In 2023, drought affected 160,000 hectares of arable land.

The total economic losses from such phenomena can be compared to the damage caused during the rise in the Caspian Sea level in 1978-1995, when the total damage amounted to about US\$2 billion. Taking into account modern infrastructure facilities and biological resources, it is predicted that by 2030, the economic risks of damage to agriculture and related industries will amount to US\$1-2 billion. As a result of these adverse factors, the GDP of coastal areas, which account for about 15-20% of the national GDP, may decline by 5-10% if measures are not taken to adapt and modernize water management systems.

Thus, coastal retreat changes natural conditions, disrupts economic activity, and creates new challenges for sustainable development.

3. Social indicators

Between 2024 and 2025, Azerbaijan's coastal regions faced significant job losses, with between 20,000 and 50,000 people losing their jobs in key sectors such as fishing, port services, and tourism. These sectors are important sources of income and social stability, especially given the current economic challenges. As a result, the unemployment rate in some coastal areas reached 10-15%, which is significantly higher than the national average.

Health and migration. The worsening environmental situation in southern Azerbaijan, linked to desertification and dust formation, is leading to an increase in respiratory diseases among the local population. In 2025, Azerbaijan recorded an increase in cases of respiratory diseases associated with exposure to dust and air pollution.

Desertification in Azerbaijan, especially in the coastal areas of the Caspian Sea, is caused by accelerated water level decline (about 2.5 m since 1995, with projections of 9-18 m by 2100), which leads to the exposure of the seabed and the formation of dust storms. These storms contain toxic dust with salts, heavy metals, and industrial pollutants (e.g., oil residues) that exacerbate respiratory problems. According to research, such dust is similar to the effects of the drying up of the Aral Sea, where there has been a 20-30% increase in respiratory diseases among the local population due to inhalation of aerosols. In Azerbaijan, this manifests itself in an increase in cases of asthma, bronchitis, pneumonia, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), especially in coastal areas with high PM10 levels such as Neftchala and Astara (Bodini et. al., 2024, Safarov et al., 2024).

In Azerbaijan's major cities, Baku and Sumgait, a 10-20% increase in PM10 (particulate matter <10 µm), SO₂, and NO₂ levels leads to a 5-15% increase in mortality from respiratory diseases. For example, during dust storms, PM10 concentrations exceed WHO standards by 2-3 times, which correlates with a 10-25% increase in hospitalizations for respiratory causes. According to the official WHO report on Azerbaijan, the average annual concentration of PM2.5 is approximately 25 µg/m³, which is 5 times higher than the WHO recommendation (WHO, 2023).

In Azerbaijan, the air quality index (AQI) often exceeds 100 in coastal areas due to PM2.5 and PM10 from dust storms, which is associated with a 20-34% increase in respiratory complaints during heat waves and droughts. Projections indicate that the effects will intensify by 2050 due to climate change: an increase in the frequency of dust storms by 20-50%, which could raise the incidence of COPD by 15% (IQAir, 2025). It is predicted that deteriorating environmental conditions could lead to the potential migration of around 50,000-100,000 people from the southern regions of the country, exacerbating internal problems with resettlement, infrastructure, and social support. Migration flows could affect the distribution of labor and public resources in neighboring regions.

Conclusion

The long-term and virtually irreversible decline in the level of the Caspian Sea requires a systematic and coordinated response from the state. This complex crisis is caused by a combination of climate change, human impact and hydrological shifts, which significantly affect Azerbaijan's coastal areas.

Analysis of data, including hydrological measurements, economic assessments and environmental forecasts, shows that the average annual decline in recent years has been around 15-30 cm. This has led to the exposure of around 38,000 hectares of land, the degradation of ecosystems and economic losses estimated at billions of dollars.

According to the Baltic Sea system, the Caspian Sea level reached a historic low of approximately -29.45 m by 2025. This increases the vulnerability of coastal areas, especially the Absheron Peninsula, where around 2.5 million people live and up to 40% of the country's economic activity is concentrated. This impacts key economic sectors, including oil and gas, fisheries, tourism and transport, and also provokes social challenges such as migration, rising unemployment and deteriorating public health. In response, Azerbaijan is collaborating with international partners, including the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), to develop and implement adaptation measures. A Plan of Action for 2025-2035 is also being developed in collaboration with the Caspian states - Azerbaijan, Russia, Iran, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan, with the aim of promoting the sustainable management of the region's water and natural resources, and protecting the region's ecosystem through cooperation. This plan's primary objective is to minimise the negative consequences of the Caspian Sea's declining water levels, protect biodiversity, ensure sustainable economic development, and strengthen coordination between regional countries. Additionally, adaptation measures in the areas of agriculture, water supply, forestry, coastal communities, human health and tourism have been identified in the country's Third National Communication to the UNFCCC (NC3) (2015).

Without timely and coordinated action, it is predicted that the sea level could fall by 8-21 metres by the end of the century. This would result in the loss of a significant portion of the sea area and exacerbate ecological and socio-economic consequences, threatening regional stability (Court, Lattuada et al., 2025).

Recommendations on how to respond to the decline in the level of the Caspian Sea include a comprehensive approach focused on adaptation and sustainable management. First and foremost, national adaptation strategies must be developed and implemented, with clear definitions of priority measures and deadlines for their implementation. Monitoring of hydrological and environmental indicators must be improved to enable the timely detection of changes and adjustments to actions. Another important area is the application of innovative engineering solutions to protect coastal infrastructure and prevent erosion.

In addition, sustainable water management must be developed, taking into account projections of changes in water levels, and scientific research aimed at understanding the complex consequences of the Caspian Sea's decline must be supported. International cooperation between the countries bordering the Caspian Sea is crucial for sharing data and coordinating joint measures. Particular attention should be paid to informing and involving local communities in adaptation and decision-making processes.

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